

A Study on Collection Development Policies of Select College Libraries Affiliated to Dibrugarh University, Upper Assam

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1. INTRODUCTION

Collection development is a systematic approach process to build library collections to meet the needs of library users, whether in an institution, college, school or public library. It is one of the most important and responsible activities in any library. Every library can be a good library if it has good service depending on the collection. The term "collection development" is the total number of library materials, general books, reference books, government documents, pamphlets, reports, punch cards, computer cassettes, and others, which constitute the collection of a library. Academic libraries are needed to make information available to all students and academic staff through a balanced collection of information resources in different formats and accessibility. Electronic resources can be purchased or access can be rented, while printed materials can be traditionally purchased or made available via document delivery.

According to the American Library Association (ALA), collection development has been defined as "a term which encompasses a number of activities related to the development of the library collection, including the determination and coordination of selection policy, assessment of needs of users and potential users, collection use studies, collection, evaluation, identification of collection needs, selection of materials, planning for resource sharing collection maintenance, and weeding".

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Harinath and Chandraiah (2017) conducted a study on the development of Dravidian university library collections from 2011 to 2016. The study finds that there is an urgent need to allocate more funds to university libraries for obtaining more e-books as well as e-journals for the use of the professional and non-professional student community of Dravidian University, Kuppam, Andhra Pradesh. Jesmi (2015) has conducted a study on collection development policies in college libraries. The policy statement should include information/documents in all subject areas in various formats. This implies that collection development policies are changing significantly, and libraries need to disseminate information about their collection policies. Koyur and Ningappa (2014) conducted a study on collection development policy in College Libraries, which is affiliated with Karnataka University. The most important function is the development of needs-based collections needed to serve the academic community and make collections widely available and encourage intensive use of collections. Arshad, Ameen and Jabeen (2021) in their study on the practice of collection development and use of printed books in Pakistani academic libraries. This study aims to reveal the practice of developing printed book collections in college libraries and patterns of using printed book collections. Samuel and Florence (2016) studied on collection development practices at the Valley View University (VVU) Library in Ghana. This study aims to determine whether there is a collection development policy in the VVU library. SPSS was used to analyze the questionnaire. The findings of this study indicate that the VVU library provides both printed and non-printed materials to its users. Marskole and Modak (2021) conducted a study on collection development in the ICT era, a case study of a private university library in the Bhopal division. This research is an attempt to determine the collection development activities in the private university library Bhopal division. Gogoi (2020) studied on the collection development in selected medical college libraries in Assam. This study was mainly conducted to examine the substantial areas and factors that influence library professionals to build effective collections for their client. Vandana (2020) has conducted a study on collection development in academic libraries. It indicates that to develop a collection in a library, library materials should be selected taking into account the current needs and the needs of future users. Library collection refers to the printed and non-printed materials in the library, new policies and principles, techniques and procedures including the complexities associated with developing collections and sorting them out. Prabhavathi and Ilanchitran (2020) in their study on libraries which are very important in academic institutions to provide timely needed information to faculty, researchers and student community to fulfill their academic needs. This paper examined the development of library collections of books, journals, budget details, status of books by subject in the library of Kakathiya University, Warangal. Patel (2016) has done his study on the importance of developing collections in libraries. Various factors must be considered when developing a qualitative collection for the benefit of the user. These factors include policies, principles, techniques and procedures, issues related to collection/ development and weeding as well. This study was attempted on the basis of experience.

3. OBJECTIVES

- To find out the status of the availability of collections in the library under study.
- To know the availability of book bank facilities in the selected college library.
- To find out the frequency of user visits to the library.
- To find out the circulation policy of selected college libraries.
- To find out the current automation scenario of selected college libraries.
- To know the availability of electronic resources in the library.
- To know the availability of library services at selected colleges.

4. METHODOLOGY

In this study, the researcher collected the necessary data from the librarian for data analysis and also presented it in the form of tables and pie charts. The questionnaires were created and distributed among the 10 college library affiliated with Dibrugarh University. To collect the necessary data, the researcher visited 10 colleges library affiliated to Dibrugarh University and observes the situation of the library. The researcher obtained necessary data from the librarian such as college history, total library collection in different disciplines, periodicity of collection development, automation, etc. All the 10 colleges completed the questionnaire correctly.

SL. No	NAME OF THE COLLEGES
1	MDKG College
2	Bahona College
3	Sibsagar College
4	Sibsagar Commerce College
5	Dr. R.K.B Law College Dibrugarh
6	Women's College, Tinsukia
7	DHSK College, Dibrugarh
8	Dibru College
9	Digboi College
10	Namrup College

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTREPRETATION

This study is an attempt to analyze and interpret data collection and services at selected colleges in Upper Assam, which are affiliated with Dibrugarh University. Questionnaires were distributed to find out the general collection development policies and procedures followed in college libraries to compare them.

5.1 Types of Colleges

Table 1: Types of Colleges

Sl. No.	No. of the Colleges	Category
1	MDKG College	Government Aided
2	Bahona College	Government
3	Sibsagar College	Government Aided
4	Sibsagar Commerce College	Government
5	Dr. R.K.B Law College Dibrugarh	Government Aided
6	Women's College, Tinsukia	Government
7	DHSK College, Dibrugarh	Government
8	Dibru College	Government Aided
9	Digboi College	Government Aided
10	Namrup College	Government Aided

From the table above illustrates that the categories of colleges we have divided the colleges into 02 categories and took them as 10 different types of colleges under the affiliation of Dibrugarh University. The categories of colleges studied for the research work are 4 Government colleges and 6 Government Aided colleges.

5.2 Distribution of Colleges based on the Year of Establishment

Table 2: Distribution of Colleges Based on Year of Establishment

Sl. No.	Name of the Colleges	Years of Establishment
1	MDKG College	1963
2	Bahona College	1966
3	Sibsagar College	1964
4	Sibsagar Commerce College	1969
5	Dr. R. K. B. Law College	1976
6	Women's College, Tinsukia	1956

7	D. H. S. K. College Dibrugarh	1945
8	Dibru College	1963
9	Digboi College	1965
10	Namrup College	1973

The table shows the year of establishment of the colleges under study.

5.3 Forms of Collection

Table 3: Forms of Collection

Name of the College	Text Books	Reference books	Project Reports	CD's	Journals	Maga-zines	News papers	Total
MDKG College	72450	26966	8	60	12	4	6	99506
Bahona College	34958	1754	122	27	6	11	8	36886
Sibsagar College	47000	25000	23	73	15	17	17	72145
Sibsagar Commerce College	15000	11000	20	80	9	11	5	26125
Dr. R.K.B Law College Dibrugarh	4500	1100	120	Nil	7	5	4	5736
Women's College, Tinsukia	17,353	27,595	4	273	22	14	9	45270
DHSK College, Dibrugarh	42616	1679	Nil	110	12	6	11	44434
Dibru College	42000	780	20	89	12	19	12	42932
Digboi College	37796	1864	Nil	Nil	8	10	7	39685
Namrup College	14000	7500	Nil	25	7	7	7	21546

5.4. Availability of Book Bank Facility

Table 4: Book Bank Facility

Sl.No.	Name of the College	Book Bank Facilities
1	MDKG College	Yes
2	Bahona College	Yes
3	Sibsagar College	Yes
4	Sibsagar Commerce College	Yes
5	Dr. R.K.B law college Dibrugarh	No

6	Women's College, Tinsukia	Yes
7	DHSK College, Dibrugarh	Yes
8	Dibru College	Yes
9	Digboi College	No
10	Namrup College	Yes

Book Bank Facility is an additional book lending facility for eligible students where they can borrow a set of books for one academic year. Most of the needy, deserving and economically poor students of the institute qualify for it. Providing a set of books helps them to get study materials for the allotted time period. A set of borrowed books is expected to be returned after the exam ends. The welfare of students is the main goal of organizing this facility.

5.5. Library Automation

Library collection automation allows libraries to be more flexible when it comes to increasing demand at peak times. Automation is also a way to prepare collections are becoming sustainable with an increasing shift to technology-based services provisions, in terms of the dissemination of information coupled with the decreasing number of funds for the library.

Table 5: Automation status of the libraries

Name of the College	Automation status
MDKG College	Partially Automated
Bahona College	Fully Automated
Sibsagar College	Fully Automated
Sibsagar Commerce College	Partially Automated
Dr. R.K.B. Law College Dibrugarh	Partially Automated
Women's College, Tinsukia	Partially Automated
DHSK College, Dibrugarh	Partially Automated
Dibru College	Partially Automated
Digboi College	Partially Automated
Namrup College	Partially Automated

Table 6: ILMS used for Library Automation

Name of the College	SOUL	KOHA
MDKG College	YES	NO
Bahona College	NO	YES
Sibsagar College	YES	NO
Sibsagar Commerce College	NO	YES
Dr. R.k.b law college Dibrugarh	NO	YES
Women's College,Tinsukia	YES	NO
DHSK College, Dibrugarh	YES	NO
Dibru College	YES	NO
Digboi College	YES	NO
Namrup College	YES	NO

From the above table, it shows that shows that Eight Colleges Library are partially automated while the Two Colleges library are fully automated. KOHA is an open-source integrated library system used in Three Colleges library (Bahona College, Sibsagar Commerce College, Dr. R.K.B. Law College Dibrugarh) and Seven Colleges library (MDKG College, Sibsagar College, Women's College,Tinsukia, DHSK College, Dibrugarh , Dibru College, Digboi College & Namrup College), are used SOUL, state-of-the-art integrated library management *software*.

5.6 Daily Users of the Library

Table 7: Users Visit Daily

Name of the College	Students	Teachers
MDKG College	86	15
Bahona College	150	20
Sibsagar College	90	10
Sibsagar Commerce College	60	6
Dr. R.K.B. Law College Dibrugarh	30	10
Women's College,Tinsukia	75	10
DHSK College, Dibrugarh	50-60	5
Dibru College	80	20
Digboi College	100-150	5
Namrup College	50	6

The library is a combination of library collections, staff and students. Users are one of the pillars of the system. The above table it shows the different categories of users who visit the library per day. User visits per day range from 5 to 150.

5. 7 Location of the Library Building

Table 8 Library Building

Name of the College	Attached with colleges building	Independent Building
MDKG College	YES	NO
Bahona College	YES	NO
Sibsagar College	NO	YES
Sibsagar Commerce College	YES	NO
Dr. R.K.B. Law College Dibrugarh	NO	YES
Women's College, Tinsukia	YES	NO
DHSK College, Dibrugarh	YES	NO
Dibru College	NO	YES
Digboi College	NO	YES
Namrup College	YES	NO

This shows the location of the library (both independent and tied to universities). 4 colleges have independent libraries with facilities. In all other colleges, the library building is part of the university building which has convenient facilities for the user community.

5.8 Availability of Library Facilities

Table 9: Library Facilities

Name of the College	Drinking Facility	Toilet Facility	AC Facility
MDKG College	YES	YES	NO
Bahona College	YES	YES	NO
Sibsagar College	YES	YES	NO
Sibsagar Commerce College	YES	NO	NO
Dr. R.K.B. Law College Dibrugarh	NO	NO	YES
Women's College, Tinsukia	YES	YES	NO
DHSK College, Dibrugarh	YES	YES	NO
Dibru College	YES	YES	NO
Digboi College	YES	YES	NO
Namrup College	YES	YES	NO

Digboi College	YES						
Namrup College	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES

The table above shows that each college has a reference service, C.A.S, Photocopying service. Some colleges do not provide Referral services, S.D.I, Bibliography services. The cost for a one-page photocopy is one rupee. The circulation of books in all colleges is carried out through the operation of computers.

5.11 Technical Processing

Table 12: Technical Processing

Name of the College	Classification	Catalogue
MDKG College	DDC	AACR II
Bahona College	DDC	AACR II
Sibsagar College	DDC	AACR II
Sibsagar Commerce College	DDC	AACR II
Dr. R.K.B. law college Dibrugarh	DDC	AACR II
Women's College, Tinsukia	DDC	AACR II
DHSK College, Dibrugarh	DDC	AACR II
Dibru College	DDC	AACR II
Digboi College	DDC	AACR II
Namrup College	DDC	AACR II

Technical services include work done behind the screen. Behind-the- screen work including acquisitions, cataloging classification and processing etc. They are fundamentally essential to the success of library activities and functions.

Technical books are the basis for server readers. They may be the same or different from library to library. But basic jobs like classification, cataloging, and photocopying are common in all colleges. To comply with the third and fourth laws, college libraries must adopt appropriate classification schemes and catalog codes. From the table, it can be seen that all universities adopt DDC and computerized catalogs.

5.12 Availability of Electronic resources in the libraries

Table 13: Availability of Electronic resources in the libraries

Name of the College	E-Books	E-Journals	E-Databases	Any Other
MDKG College	YES	YES	NO	NO
Bahona College	YES	YES	YES	NO
Sibsagar College	YES	YES	YES	NO
Sibsagar Commerce College	YES	YES	YES	YES
Dr. R.k.b law college Dibrugarh	NO	NO	NO	NO
Women's College, Tinsukia	NO	NO	YES	NO
DHSK College, Dibrugarh	YES	YES	NO	NO
Dibru College	YES	YES	NO	NO
Digboi College	YES	YES	NO	NO
Namrup College	YES	YES	NO	NO

6. SUGGESTIONS

1. The government colleges should bring major changes in the library by following the collection development policies of almost all colleges under the jurisdiction of Dibrugarh University, Upper Assam.
2. There is a need for uniformity and standard collection development policies in college libraries which are under the affiliation of Dibrugarh University, Upper Assam
3. It is imperative that universities should make such steps to the college library that every college should update their collections in consultation with Dibrugarh University, Upper Assam.
4. The government colleges and government aided colleges should carry out more library activities and actively participate in collection development policies and resource sharing activities.
5. The colleges should consult more with bibliographic tools before obtaining books and other reading materials.
6. The College libraries must update their collections with increased purchases, collection developments and other electronic media.
7. Universities should be more regulated about college collections in terms of references and other books.

8. It is recommended to government colleges and other private aided colleges to increase library staff, so that they can provide better services to users.

7. CONCLUSION

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the collection development policy in the library of the selected colleges in order to identify the availability of resources. The development of collections and academic libraries is a complex and important activity to provide an infrastructure in which users can acquire the information they need. This requires the formulation of clear goals and policies that must be consistent with the library's and institution's objectives and mission as a whole. The primary responsibility for collection development lies with the library's bibliography, which is aided in decision making by academics.

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